

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Gluons Confinement

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and in particular the topic of Quark confinement it is possible the reason why Gluons are confined as well. In contrast to Quarks, gluons are net curvature unbound; they can leave the curvature hyperbole trapping the quarks. The curvature hyperbole is attracting weaker curvatures and thus produce the effect of trapping the Gluons as well.

Introduction

First, we can represent the original equation, which regard Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup +1$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.21)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

We have proven the invariant three to be an electron and the process of propagation for the third term is given by equation (1.3):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.3)$$

Fermions are described by the arbitrary variation term on the main equation (1.4). By discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.41), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements that differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.41)$$

Bosons are mentioned in the first paragraph are described as net curvature, given by the term (1.4) of the photon for example. Now, we have used the visualization of the sea of gluons on the Quark triplet in the following way.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.4)$$

When we indulge in high energy collisions that is synonymous with trying to roll the quark triplet uphill. It is possible to try as the bosons are just net curvature unbound as given by (1), however since each boson is a curvature of certain magnitude it increase the probability of arrival to its position, therefore we have a "sea" of gluons. That was the analysis in the context of Quark confinement. Now assume we have a positive summation of Gluons trapping a Quark triplet in the above hyperbole. Assume there is no restriction regarding Gluons, one of them leaves the hyperbole.

$$\sum_{i=1}^K g_i = \sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \delta g_i \quad (1.4)$$

Since there are a sea of gluons, and one free gluon, which just left, the gluon that just left could be replaced by another Gluon or alternatively are re-attracted to the hyperbole just as larger masses attract smaller masses, as an analog. Strong curvature clusters pull weaker curvature or free curvatures. The pull is not restricted only to fermions such as Quarks. In that way we could explain the phenomena of Gluon confinement.

One final point, since there are eight gluon fields, we should be able to describe the interaction on the matrix tensor between each Gluon type. In other words, given two net curvatures unbound which somehow differ in their nature, the matrix tensor itself may produce a mediator in between, so this mediator may be regarded as a physical entity, which could or could not manifest as a new particle. Such description are currently not within the domains of description of the 8T. That raises another question, how can two net curvatures on the matrix tensor exactly differ from one another assuming they are all isomorphic to the same discrete number, i.e. $+(1)$?

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)